

Retention behavior of amino acids on plain, tri-*n*-butyl phosphate and tri-*n*-butylamine impregnated silica gel-G layers in mixed mobile phases

S. D. Sharma*, Himanshu Sharma and Sumesh Chandra Sharma

Analytical Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, B-3, Jigar Colony, Moradabad-244 001, India

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The retention behavior of twenty four amino acids has been examined on plain, tri-*n*-butyl phosphate (TBP) and tri-*n*-butylamine (TBA) impregnated silica gel-G layers using butanol-acetic acid and acetone-benzene-acetic acid mixtures in varying ratios as the mobile phases. The effects of TBP and TBA impregnation and mobile phase composition on R_f values are discussed. The butanol-acetic acid (6 : 4) used as mobile phase has been found most effective in the separation of L-lysine-HCl from other amino acids. Quantitative separations of L-lysine-HCl from drug samples are carried out in this media.

TLC of metal ions has been successfully carried out by us on tri-*n*-butyl phosphate (TBP) and tri-*n*-butylamine (TBA) impregnated silica gel-G layers¹. However, these layers have not been used for the study of chromatographic behavior of amino acids. Reversed phase thin layer chromatography (RPTLC) of amino acids on such layers using varying ratios of butanol-acetic acid and acetone-benzene-acetic acid as mobile phase has been carried out. As a result, some useful separations have been realized. Butanol was chosen owing to our earlier experience² and butanol-acetic acid media has been found useful in effecting a large number of amino acid separations on titanium(IV) arsenate papers³.

Results and Discussion

In the RPTLC of amino acids on TBP and TBA impregnated silica gel-G layers, most of the spots are well-defined and compact and tailing is observed only for (a) (Lys), His, Val and Ser in mobile phases (M_4 and M_{11}), M_9 , M_{10} and M_{13} , respectively, on TBP impregnated layers, (b) Hyd, Val (Ala, Lys and Leu) and (Thr) in mobile phases M_5 , M_7 , (M_{11}) and (M_7 , M_{15} and M_{18}), respectively, on TBA impregnated layers. Furthermore, the spots are well-defined and more compact on TBP impregnated layers than on TBA impregnated ones. In order to check reproducibility of the results, the R_f values taken in butanol-acetic acid (4 : 6) mobile phase were found to be reproducible and the variation does not exceed 5% of the average R_f value.

The impregnated layers are quite stable and firm, and are capable of withstanding the mobile phases and chemical operations. The development time (6–7 h) for 60 and 80% impregnation is much higher as compared to that for 20 and 40% impregnation (1–2 h). On the basis of develop-

ment time and compactness of spots, 40% impregnated layers were therefore chosen for chromatography.

It is interesting to investigate the effect of TBP and TBA impregnation on the R_f values of amino acids in butanol-acetic acid (5 : 5) media. The plots of R_f vs percentage impregnation of TBP and TBA reveal following conclusions.

The R_f values for all amino acids are sufficiently higher on unimpregnated layers than on impregnated ones. However, R_f values decrease with an increase in percentage impregnation of TBP and for most of the amino acids the R_f is minimum at 60% TBP impregnation probably due to strong adsorption. Beyond this, the R_f slightly increases, which may be attributed to lesser adsorption of amino acids due to an increase in the non-polar nature of the layers. L-Cysteine-HCl shows an irregular trend as compared to other amino acids. This is probably due to the presence of SH group in its molecule. The R_f values for all amino acids on TBA impregnated layers are higher than that on TBP impregnated ones. This difference in the R_f is probably due to the polar nature of TBP layers which causes polar-polar interactions with amino acids, resulting in lower R_f . The TBP impregnated layers are more polar than the TBA impregnated ones. TBP is slightly soluble in water (0.04 per 100 parts at 20°) whereas TBA is almost insoluble.

On TBA impregnated layers, for amino acids such as L-glycine, DL-alanine, DL-2-aminobutyric acid, DL-serine, DL-threonine, DL-isoleucine, DL-methionine, DL- β -phenylalanine, DL-tryptophan, DL-aspartic acid and L-glutamic acid, there is slight variation in the R_f values with an increase in TBA impregnation thereby suggesting no specific interaction of the amino acids with these layers. The R_f values for

L-proline, L-cysteine-HCl, L-cystine, L-tyrosine and L-ornithine-HCl decrease upto 40% TBA impregnation. However, the decrease is more pronounced for L-cysteine-HCl. It may be due to some specific interaction of these amino acids with 40% TBA impregnated layers. The R_F values of DL-valine, DL-DOPA and DL-tryptophan slightly decrease as the percentage impregnation of TBA reaches 20%. Beyond this, the effect of impregnation is almost negligible and R_F remains almost constant.

The R_F values of L-hydroxyproline, DL-norleucine, L-lysine-HCl, L-histidine and L-arginine show a continuous decrease with increase in percentage impregnation of TBA. It may be due to some interaction with TBA thereby causing a decrease in R_F . However, L-lysine-HCl, L-histidine and L-arginine show lower R_F irrespective of the extent of impregnation. It is probably due to the presence of extra NH_2 group in these amino acids.

The amino acids, such as DL-alanine and DL-serine show continuous decrease in R_F upto 60% TBA impregnation and beyond which, the R_F value increases only slightly. This shows that most of the amino acids exhibit some specific interaction at 60% impregnation.

Effect of mobile phase composition on R_F :

To study the effect of mobile phase composition on R_F for unimpregnated as well as TBP and TBA impregnated layers, R_F vs mobile phase composition plots were drawn for all the amino acids (figures not given for the sake of brevity). The conclusions are given below.

Butanol-acetic acid media : For all amino acids, the R_F value generally increases with an increase in the mole fraction of acetic acid on impregnated and unimpregnated layers. This may be attributed to an increase in the polar nature of the mobile phases. The chromatographic behavior of all the amino acids on TBP impregnated layers is quite revealing as the neutral and acidic amino acids show much lower R_F irrespective of mobile phase composition. It may be due to the higher adsorption of these acids on TBP impregnated layers. However, DL-methionine and L-cysteine show anomalous behavior on these impregnated layers. Similarly, L-cysteine-HCl and L-cystine also show irregular trend on unimpregnated and TBA impregnated layers, probably due to the presence of sulfur atom in these amino acids. The R_F values of basic amino acids are higher on TBP impregnated layers than on unimpregnated ones except for L-ornithine-HCl. This may be due to the fact that these amino acids interact less strongly with the adsorbent surface due to the presence of extra- NH_2 group resulting in an increase in R_F .

On TBA impregnated layers, R_F values for almost all

the amino acids in *n*-butanol is low ($R_F \leq 0.20$). This is due to much lower solubility of amino acids in *n*-butanol. However, with addition of acetic acid, a sudden increase in R_F is noticed due to an increase in the polarity of the mobile phase causing higher solvation of amino acids. All the basic amino acids show similar behavior and give higher R_F on TBA impregnated layers except for L-ornithine-HCl which is strongly adsorbed on these layers resulting in lower R_F . For acidic amino acids, i.e. DL-aspartic acid and L-glutamic acid, the R_F values on these layers are slightly higher than neutral and basic amino acids in pure butanol media. But on addition of acetic acid, the R_F value sharply increases upto the stage when butanol-acetic acid composition becomes 9 : 1. This may be due to the fact that increase in acetic acid concentration facilitates the partition of solute in mobile phase and hence increase in R_F observed. On further increasing the acetic acid concentration the R_F remains almost constant.

Acetone-benzene-acetic acid media : To study the effect of mobile phase composition on average R_F values in three-component mobile phases, plots of average R_F vs mobile phase composition were drawn. The salient features are as follows.

(i) *Effect of mole fraction of acetone :* It is observed that on unimpregnated and TBA impregnated layers the average R_F values are higher than on TBP impregnated ones irrespective of the mobile phase composition. The difference in average R_F on two impregnated layers is probably due to almost non-polar nature of TBA impregnated layers (TBP impregnated layers are slightly polar) thereby causing lesser adsorption of the various amino acids resulting in higher R_F values. On TBP impregnated layers, an increase in acetone concentration gradually but slightly increases the average R_F . This can be attributed to the slight increase of the polarity of the mobile phase as acetone is slightly polar. On unimpregnated and TBA impregnated layers, the behavior of amino acids is almost the same. On these layers, the average R_F is not much affected by an increase in acetone concentration. However, the value suddenly decreases only when the acetic acid concentration starts decreasing along with an increase in acetone concentration, thereby decreasing the polar nature of the mobile phase. Here the slight increase in polarity due to increase in acetone concentration plays a significant role.

(ii) *Effect of mole fraction of benzene :* As the benzene concentration in the mobile phase increases, the acetic acid concentration decreases, thereby decreasing the polar nature of the mobile phase which results in a gradual decrease in R_F on all the three layers. However, the extent of decrease

is much higher on unimpregnated layers probably due to higher adsorption of amino acids on them.

(iii) *Effect of mole fraction of acetic acid* : It is observed that R_F value increases with an increase in acetic acid concentration in the mobile phase. On unimpregnated layers the average R_F value sharply increases as the effect of mobile phase polarity governs the interaction of amino acids with the stationary phase. As the acetic acid concentration increases, the polarity of the mobile phase also increases and thus due to higher solvation of amino acids in the mobile phase, the R_F value sharply increases. The increase in R_F on impregnated layers is gradual but slow as the amino acids move under the combined influence of mobile phase and impregnated layers. The average R_F on TBP impregnated layers is much lower than on TBA impregnated ones due to the fact that TBP impregnated layer being relatively more polar adsorbs the amino acids more strongly resulting in lower R_F .

Finally, as a result of differential migration of various amino acids, L-lysine-HCl has been separated from L-leucine, DL-threonine, DL-isoleucine and DL-tryptophan in butanol-acetic acid (9 : 1) and from DL-methionine in butanol-acetic acid (7 : 3) mobile phases on TBA impregnated silica gel-G layers. These amino acids are present in Astymin (liquid) alongwith L-lysine-HCl. An important advantage of this work lies in the quantitative separation of L-lysine-HCl from drug samples containing varying amounts of seven other amino acids (in case of Astymin 'liquid' as given in Table 1) on silica gel-G layers in butanol-acetic acid (6 : 4) media. The method works satisfactorily even in the separation of L-lysine-HCl from Incremin (liquid).

Table 1. Determination of L-lysine-HCl in drug samples*

Drug	Labelled amount of amino acids in drug (mg)	Amount (μ g)		% Deviation
		Taken	Found	
Incremin (Liquid)	L-Lysine HCl = (150) in 5 ml of the sample	30.00	31.00	+3.33
Astymin (Liquid)	L-Lysine HCl = (25) in 15 ml of the sample	50.00	48.00	-4.00
Astymin (Capsule)	L-Lysine HCl = (25) per capsule	50.00 ^a	49.15 ^a	-1.70

*Each result is average of three replicas.

^aValues reported in the literature (Ref. 5).

Experimental

Silica gel-G, TBP, TBA and other chemicals were of A.R. grade.

A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer was used.

Preparation of chromatoplates and detector were the same as reported earlier⁴. The amino acid used were L-glycine (Gly), L-hydroxyproline (Hyd), DL-alanine (Ala), DL-2-aminobutyric acid (*n*-But), DL-serine (Ser), L-proline (Pro), DL-valine (Val), DL-threonine (Thr), L-cysteine-HCl (Cyst), L-leucine (Leu), DL-isoleucine (Ile), DL-norleucine (*n*-Leu), DL-methionine (Met), L-tyrosine (Tyr), DL- β -phenylalanine (β -Phe), L-tryptophan (Trp), DL-dihydroxyphenylalanine (DOPA), L-cystine (Cys), L-ornithine-HCl (Orn), L-lysine-HCl (Lys), L-histidine-HCl (His), L-arginine (Arg), DL-aspartic acid (Asp) and L-glutamic acid (Glu). Solutions (0.1%) of these amino acids in water were prepared as reported earlier⁴.

Twentyfour amino acids were chromatographed in following nineteen solvent systems used as mobile phases : (a) butanol-acetic acid mixtures in following proportions : M₁, 10 : 0; M₂, 9 : 1; M₃, 8 : 2; M₄, 7 : 3; M₅, 6 : 4; M₆, 5 : 5; M₇, 4 : 6; M₈, 3 : 7; M₉, 2 : 8; M₁₀, 1 : 9; M₁₁, 0 : 10, and (b) acetone-benzene-acetic acid mixtures in following proportions : M₁₂, 4 : 5 : 1; M₁₃, 4 : 4 : 2; M₁₄, 4 : 3 : 3; M₁₅, 4 : 2 : 4; M₁₆, 5 : 1 : 4; M₁₇, 6 : 1 : 3; M₁₈, 7 : 1 : 2 and M₁₉, 8 : 1 : 1.

Procedure :

For qualitative analysis : After development, the chromatograms were oven dried at 100°, sprayed with 0.2% ninhydrin in acetone and heated again for 5 min or more to detect the amino acids as coloured spots against white background.

For quantitative analysis : The samples, i.e. Astymin (liquid) and Incremin (liquid) were spotted on the plates with a micropipette and the development was made as usual. Pilot chromatograms were run under similar conditions to ascertain the actual position of the spots on pilot plates which were detected using the ninhydrin reagent. The same portion of the experimental plates was then scratched out and the amino acids present in these portions were extracted with small volume of absolute alcohol, 5 ml being used for complete elution.

Determination of amino acids present in the drug samples was carried out by the standard ninhydrin method as follows. A mixture of the sample solution (1 ml) and ninhydrin reagent (1 ml) was heated in a boiling water-bath for ~20 min. The diluting solution (equal volumes of GDW and 1-propanol; 5 ml) was then mixed with it. A blank was also run. After cooling, the solution was further diluted to 10 ml with the diluting solution. The absorbance of the purple colour so developed was measured at 570 nm⁵ and the amount of L-lysine-HCl present determined with the help of calibration curve.

References

1. S. D. Sharma, S. Misra and S. C. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 81; S. D. Sharma and S. C. Sharma, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1999, **841**, 263; *J. Plannar Chromatogr.*, 2000, **13**, 93.
2. M. Qureshi and S. D. Sharma, *Anal. Chem.*, 1973, **45**, 1283.
3. M. Qureshi, S. A. Nabi and N. Zehra, *Sep. Sci.*, 1975, **10**, 801.
4. R. Bhushan in "Handbook of Thin Layer Chromatography", eds. J. Sharma and B. Fried, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1991 and 1996.
5. K. G. Varshney, A. A. Khan, S. M. Maheshwari and U. Gupta, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1992, **65**, 2773.